

**IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE
LEGAL BASIS OF THE ARMED FORCES**

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The article analyzes the formation and development of legal documents regulating the activities of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and gives theoretical conclusions and proposals related to the systematization of military legal relations in the future.

Keywords: military legislation, Armed Forces, declaration, foreign policy, etc.

After the independence of our country, extensive reforms are being implemented in all spheres. Independence allows our people to determine their own destiny, to exercise their rights and freedoms without any obstacles, to serve the interests of the people and not to state agencies, to own their own property, to be a humane democratic state, made it possible to establish an open and fair society.

From the first days of our independence, to strengthen the foundations of state sovereignty, to create a national legislative system that legally regulates social relations in all areas based on international standards, to ensure the supremacy of the constitution and laws in a single legal space, to conduct foreign policy as a full and equal subject of international relations. , democratic reforms were implemented in all areas, such as ensuring the country's defense and security. In particular, reforms related to the reform of the Armed Forces system, the formation of a modern army, the training of professional military personnel who can quickly and independently make correct decisions in complex and urgent situations, and the strengthening and development of the legal basis of the Armed Forces' activities are among these.

We can conditionally divide the formation and development of the legal bases of the Armed Forces into several stages and analyze them.

The first step can be explained by the "Declaration of Independence" adopted on June 20,

1990. After all, in Article 1 of the Declaration, the rule that "the independence of the democratic state of the Uzbek SSR is the sole authority of the republic in its territory in all its constituent parts and in all external relations" shall be carried out over indivisible parts..."[1] priority rules are defined. It follows from this that it is explained by the fact that the republic has taken under its jurisdiction all the constituent parts of its territory, in particular, the military units and institutions of the Armed Forces.

The second step can be explained by the adoption of the constitutional law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the foundations of state independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated August 31, 1991. Because, in Article 6 of this Constitutional Law, "The Republic of Uzbekistan has the right to establish the Ministry of Defense, to establish the National Guard and non-military (alternative) service . "[2] important vital rules are defined that the sovereign reserves the right to implement military policy on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan in matters of forming and leading the Armed Forces of the USSR". In fact, with this constitutional law, the military policy related to the formation and leadership of military units that ensure defense and security in the territory of the country, are a guarantee of state sovereignty and territorial integrity, and are fully under their independent jurisdiction. legally guaranteed that he received it.

The third step can be explained by the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Defense"[3] adopted on July 3, 1992. With this Law, the organization of defense and the leadership of the Armed Forces, the powers of state bodies in the field of defense, the self-government bodies of citizens, enterprises, institutions, organizations and the participation of citizens in ensuring defense, state of war, wartime, mobilization, important military legal relations such as territorial defense, armed conflicts, and international cooperation in the field of defense are regulated. With the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 211-II dated May 11, 2001, the Law "On Defense" was adopted in a new version.

of the fourth important steps can be explained by the adoption of the "Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan[4]" of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan on December 8, 1992. Already, the leadership rules for organizing the activities of the Armed Forces have been strengthened in our General Council. In particular, chapter 27 of our updated Constitution defines the constitutional foundations of defense and security, and according to Article 152, " The Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan are formed to protect the state sovereignty and

territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, peaceful life and security of the population. " . "The structure of the Armed Forces and their organization shall be determined by law", while [Article 153 states the governing rules](#) " The Republic of Uzbekistan has sufficient Armed Forces to ensure its security". Also, according to the Basic Law, "Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the duty of every citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan." Citizens are obliged to perform military or alternative service according to the law" [4].

The fifth step can be explained by the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On General Military Obligation and Military Service" adopted on December 12, 2002. Because with this law, the legislation on military obligation and military service, types of military service, military positions, preparation of citizens for military service, registration of citizens at conscription stations, conscription and entry into military service, military service, reserve military legal relations such as service, alternative service, military list, conscription for mobilization and dismissal from military service are regulated.

The sixth step can be explained by the Law No. 478-II[5] "On service in the reserve of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on April 25, 2003. With this Law, legislation on service in the reserve of the Armed Forces , reserve categories, selection of reservists, training of reservists, a number of military relations, such as types of military gatherings, military ranks of reservists, are regulated.

The seventh step can be explained by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 9, 2018 "On the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan"[6]. With this Law, the specific features of the military-political situation, the main threats to national security in the military sphere, the defense policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the nature of modern military conflicts, the main directions of preparing the country for possible military conflicts, the armed forces, their main tasks and the basis of their application, actions of the armed forces to protect the population and objects from emergency situations, leading the defense of the country and the armed forces, the main tasks and directions of the development of the state military organization, military-economic aspects of the country's defense military legal relations related to the bases of security, mobilization readiness of the country, defense industry complex of the country are regulated.

this article are the legal documents regulating the activities of the Armed Forces. At the same time, the main documents that regulate the activities of the Armed Forces and ensure the implementation of the mentioned law are the legal documents. In particular, PQ-1571 dated August 19, 2005 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve

the system of social protection of military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan", PQ-694 dated May 31, 2012 "On approval of the Regulation on the procedure for providing housing to the military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan", No. PQ-1765 of May 31, 2012 "Conditional military service in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the system of benefits for the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PQ-4447 of September 12, 2019 "On approval" and Decree No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of NEW Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" are among them.

In the development strategy, strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy is defined as one of the most important priorities.

This priority direction aims to further strengthen the state's defense capabilities, increase the combat readiness of the Armed Forces, its capabilities and capabilities, and comprehensively strengthen the social protection of military personnel and their family members.

Based on the above, we can come to several theoretical conclusions:

first , the adopted legislative documents served as a legal guarantee for the formation and development of our national army;

secondly, based on the concept of norm creation and the tasks defined in the Development Strategy to reduce as much as possible the legal documents regulating social relations and to adopt directly applicable legal documents, the Republic of Uzbekistan it is expedient to define the norms defined in the regulation on the procedure of military service of citizens at the level of a legal document, that is, to develop a draft law on the procedure of military service of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

thirdly, relations related to the legal status of military personnel in our country are regulated by various laws and regulations, which are interpreted differently for military personnel of the Armed Forces (for example, social protection of military personnel, senior issues with pension provision), that is, further systematization is desirable. Based on this, it is appropriate to adopt a single legal document defining the legal status of military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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